

D 2.5 IMPLEMENTATION OF THE NUMERICAL RESOLUTION SCHEME

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Contents

1	Large Deformation Cosserat	5
1.1	Recalls of Algebraic Rotations	5
1.2	Cosserat Kinematics	7
1.3	Balance Laws	9
1.4	Constitutive Behavior	10
1.5	Problem Discretization	12
1.6	Constructing the Material Tangent Matrix	15
1.6.1	Consequences of the Plane Strain assumption	16
2	Tests	20
2.1	Homogeneous Fields - Single Element Tests	20
2.1.1	Tension Test	20
2.1.2	Glide Test	22
2.2	Simple Micro-rotation Boundary Layer	22
A		25
A.1	Recalls of Tensorial Algebra and Tensorial Differentiation	25

Introduction

This report embodies the Deliverable 2.5 titled "Implementation of the numerical resolution scheme" developed within the European Project ENABLE, a Marie-Curie Skłodowska ITN funded by the European Union under the grant n° 764979. This manuscript contains the description of the theoretical framework that will be used to simulate machining operations enhanced with strain gradient. After a thorough literature investigations on the strain gradient theories, pros and cons of the available theories have been evaluated, and the Cosserat theory was chosen as the most favorable theory to be used [1]. By exploring the implications related to the numerical implementation of each theory in a *Finite Element* (FE) environment, the Cosserat theory has been elected as the most simple and straightforward theory to be adopted, thanks to the way the strain gradient terms are handled. The choice has been strongly influenced by the requirement of employing these theories in a Large Deformation framework.

The following report is divided in two chapters, the first one discusses the theory and its discretization aimed toward a FE implementation, and the second one contains the numerical tests that have been performed to verify and assess the accuracy and correctness of the solution. The first chapter starts by giving the reader the instruments required to understand the derivations contained in the description and discretization of the theory. The parametrization of the rotation operation in a three dimensional space will be discussed and the choice of the parametrization solution will be presented. Successively, the Cosserat theory in a Large Deformation framework will be presented, and its numerical discretization will be accurately discussed. Many models of Cosserat in Large Deformation can be found in literature [2–11], few discussed their numerical implementation in a FE environment [12, 13], none of them pursued the direction that has been chosen and described in this manuscript, hence the novelty. The second part of the report presents the verifications procedure adopted for the developed FE.

Chapter 1

Large Deformation Cosserat

In classical continuum mechanics the transition from *Small Deformation* (SD) to *Large Deformation* (LD) involves a modification in the way the strain is measured, and in the assumption that the domain occupied by the medium stays unchanged. Since the Cosserat continuum is endowed with rotational degrees of freedom, the rotational-related deformation measures must be evaluated while taking into account that the assumptions holding for SD framework are no longer valid in LD. This represents a non-negligible feature of this theory, therefore, the next section aims at feeding the reader with the information required to handle deformation measures in a LD scenario.

1.1 Recalls of Algebraic Rotations

Rigid rotations in a three-dimensional Euclidean space $\{\mathbf{e}_1; \mathbf{e}_2; \mathbf{e}_3\}$ endowed with Cartesian norm are isomorphic transformations $\mathcal{R}^3 \rightarrow \mathcal{R}^3$, and they can be uniquely identified through a set of three independent parameters, which can be identified with the direction of the axis of rotation and the angle of rotation. Being rotations characterized by a direction and a scalar, it might be thought that using first order tensors in a three-dimensional space would be an adequate choice to describe them. However, if vectors were used to represent the rotation (where its direction individuates the axis of rotation, its modulus is the angle of rotation and the right-hand rule was considered to identify positive rotations), some basic properties which are valid in the three-dimensional Euclidean vectorial space would be violated, e.g the commutative property. Therefore, the representation of rotation operators cannot be handled through vectors. Nonetheless, there exists particular first order tensors which can be used for this purpose, and they are called *pseudo-vectors*. They behave as normal vectors under a proper rotation but they change their direction under an improper rotation (e.g. reflection). A pseudo-vector $\underline{\boldsymbol{\theta}}$ has the following form:

$$\underline{\boldsymbol{\theta}} = \theta \hat{\mathbf{n}}; \quad (1.1)$$

where θ is the modulus of the pseudo-vector and $\hat{\mathbf{n}}$ is the unit vector of $\underline{\boldsymbol{\theta}}$ indicating the direction around which the rotation operates. However, although there exist a unique pseudo-vector for each and every three-dimensional rotation, pseudo-vectors cannot be directly employed to perform a rotation operation. In order to do so, a rotation operator is required, this being represented by second order tensors, also referred to as *rotation matrices*. One way to retrieve the rotation operator from the pseudo-vectors of rotation is through the adoption of the following:

$$\underline{\mathbf{R}} = \exp(\underline{\boldsymbol{\theta}}_{\times}) = \exp\left(-\underline{\boldsymbol{\epsilon}} \cdot \underline{\boldsymbol{\theta}}_{\times}\right) = \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} \frac{\underline{\boldsymbol{\theta}}_{\times}^n}{n!}; \quad (1.2)$$

which can also be expressed with the well known *Rodrigues formula*:

$$\underline{\mathbf{R}} = \underline{\mathbf{I}} + \frac{\sin \theta}{\theta} \underline{\boldsymbol{\theta}}_{\times} + \frac{1 - \cos \theta}{\theta^2} \underline{\boldsymbol{\theta}}_{\times} \cdot \underline{\boldsymbol{\theta}}_{\times}; \quad (1.3)$$

where $\underline{\theta}_{\times}$ is the skew-symmetric second order tensor associated with the rotation vector $\underline{\theta}$ that can be obtained as defined in Equation A.6. However, using pseudo-vectors is only one of the possible ways to describe the rotation matrix. Many other methods are used in different areas such as robotics, video games programming and others, where the description of large angles is involved. Every description is based on a different parametrization of the rotation. Parameterizing the rotation is a useful procedure which can facilitate the numerical implementation of a code that deals with large rotations.

In general, rotation parameterization can be distinguished between vectorial and non-vectorial parameterization, depending on the number of parameters used. The minimum set of independent parameters is three, and every form of parametrizaion that uses only three parametrs belongs to the group of vectorial parameterization. Other solutions that use more than three parameters, e.g. quaternions, are part of the non-vectorial rotation parameterizations. The parameter vector is a generalization of the pseudo-vector defined in Equation 1.1, written as:

$$\underline{p} = p(\theta) \hat{\underline{n}}; \quad (1.4)$$

where $p(\theta)$ is the *generating function* and $\hat{\underline{n}}$ is the unit vector defining the direction around which the rotation takes place. It can be observed that Equation 1.1 can be retrieved by choosing the angle θ itself as the generating function; this parameterization is called *Cartesian Rotation vector*. Choosing a different generating function therefore is equivalent to choosing a different parameterization. The most common rotation parameterizations are summarized in Table 1.1.

Parametrization	$p(\theta)$	ν	ε	Defined in
Cartesian Rotation Vector	θ	$\left[\sin \frac{\theta}{2} \right] / \left[\frac{\theta}{2} \right]$	$\left[\tan \frac{\theta}{2} \right] / \left[\frac{\theta}{2} \right]$	$ \theta < 2\pi$
Linear	$\sin(\theta)$	$\cos^{-1}\left(\frac{\theta}{2}\right)$	$\cos^{-2}\left(\frac{\theta}{2}\right)$	$ \theta < \pi$
Euler Rodrigues	$2 \sin\left(\frac{\theta}{2}\right)$	1	$\cos^{-1}\left(\frac{\theta}{2}\right)$	$ \theta < \pi$
Cayley-Gibbs-Rodrigues	$2 \tan\left(\frac{\theta}{2}\right)$	$\cos\left(\frac{\theta}{2}\right)$	1	$ \theta < \pi$
Wiener-Milenkovic	$4 \tan(\theta/4)$	$\cos^2\left(\frac{\theta}{4}\right)$	$\left[1 - \tan^2\left(\frac{\theta}{4}\right)\right]^{-1}$	$ \theta < 2\pi$

Table 1.1: Parametrization methods.

Equation 1.2 is a specif form of the Rorigues formula that corresponds to the choice of the Cartesian Rotation Vector parametrization. However, the general form of the Rodrigues formula for the vectorial parametrization is the following:

$$\underline{\mathbf{R}} = \underline{\mathbf{I}} + \zeta_1(\theta)\underline{p}_{\times} + \zeta_2(\theta)\underline{p}_{\times} \cdot \underline{p}_{\times}; \quad (1.5)$$

where:

$$\zeta_1(\theta) = \frac{\nu^2}{\varepsilon}; \quad (1.6)$$

$$\zeta_2(\theta) = \frac{\nu^2}{2}; \quad (1.7)$$

and the values of ν and ε are indicated in the Table 1.1 for different types of parameterization. The advantage of parametrizing the rotation operation is mainly in the reduced number of independent parametrs

Figure 1.1: Schematic representation of the difference between Cosserat and Classical continuum. The external square is inertial to the material thus representing the material rotation, while the internal circle with the arrow is inertial to the microstructure, thus representing the microstructure orientation. Undeformed continuum (a), deformed continuum in the classical continuum mechanics description (b), deformed continuum in the Cosserat description (c).

that identify the rotation, and this lead in a reduced effort in terms of memory whether the rotation was to be modelled numerically. For instance, in case of the large rotations experienced by the Cosserat continuum, we would enhance the continuum with only three additional degrees of freedom, being the components of the pseudo-vector $\underline{\theta}$. **In this manuscript we chose to use a Cartesian Rotation Vector to parametrize the rotation.**

1.2 Cosserat Kinematics

In an Euclidean three-dimensional space, on which a Cartesian metric is defined $\{\mathbf{e}_1; \mathbf{e}_2; \mathbf{e}_3\}$, we identify a continuous bounded region Ω as our domain of interest. Our purpose is to characterize the evolution of the motion of our domain of interest in time. Let us consider an initial time t_0 at which the position and state variables, to be defined later, of the body are known. In this context, right subscripts indicate the time at which the quantity is evaluated, e.g. Ω_0 is our domain of interest at time 0.

At every time, all the points of the domain are endowed with three *degrees of freedom* (d.o.f.) that are the Cartesian coordinates of the point. At time t , the position vector that contains these d.o.f. is written as \mathbf{x}_t or simply \mathbf{x} . We chose to set the initial configuration as reference, practically describing the problem from a Lagrangian perspective, and the position vector belonging to this configuration is referred to as \mathbf{x}_0 or simply \mathbf{X} . In the Cosserat description of the continuum, every point of the domain of interest does not only possess a position in the space, but also an orientation with the respect to an inertial frame of reference. A triad of directors is attached to every point in the domain, describing the continuum orientation in the Euclidean space, which suits perfectly to the purpose of describing lattice orientation.

The main conceptual difference between the Classical and the Cosserat description of the Continuum is that while the latter allows the microstructure to rotate independently from the material, the former enforces a constrain over these two rotations, *de facto* imposing them to be equal. Hence, the main feature of the Cosserat theory is to effectively decouple the material rotation and the microstructure rotation. Figure 1.1 shows the difference between the two models in term of rotation.

Following the discussion regarding the rotations, from Equation 1.2 it is clear that although the rotation operator is a second order tensor, $\underline{\mathbf{R}}$, the body is endowed with only three additional degrees of freedom, being the three parameters of the Cartesian Rotation Vector, meant to represent the rotation of the microstructure orientation with respect an inertial frame of reference (these three d.o.f.s are the variables of the three-dimensional Lie group associated to the rotation $\underline{\mathbf{R}}$). At time t these d.o.f. are embraced in the vector $\underline{\theta}$:

$$\underline{\mathbf{R}} = \exp\left(\underline{\boldsymbol{\theta}}_{\times}\right) = \exp\left(-\underline{\boldsymbol{\epsilon}} \cdot \underline{\boldsymbol{\omega}}\right); \quad (1.8)$$

As in standard continuum mechanics, the evaluation of the deformation related to the displacement is performed by computing the variation of the position vector at time t with respect to the variation of the position vector at time 0:

$$\underline{\mathbf{F}} = \frac{d\mathbf{x}}{d\mathbf{X}} = \underline{\mathbf{x}} \otimes \underline{\nabla}_0; \quad (1.9)$$

where $\underline{\mathbf{F}}$ is the *deformation gradient* and its determinant is the Jacobian of the transformation $J = \det(\underline{\mathbf{F}})$. The Cosserat description of the media does not require only the deformation gradient and the rotation matrix as measure of the media distortion, but it also requires the following quantity to fully describe the state of the continuum:

$$\underline{\boldsymbol{\Gamma}} = \frac{1}{2} \underline{\boldsymbol{\epsilon}} : \left[\underline{\mathbf{R}} \cdot \left(\underline{\mathbf{R}}^T \otimes \underline{\nabla}_0 \right) \right]; \quad (1.10)$$

which is referred to as *wryness*. Equation 1.10 quantifies the gradient of the rotation tensors in a Lagrangian framework, and it is possible to describe it by a second order tensor because the rotation operation has only three independent parameters. By defining the displacement field as $\underline{\mathbf{u}} = \underline{\mathbf{X}} - \underline{\mathbf{x}}$, we can consequently define:

$$\underline{\mathbf{v}} = \dot{\underline{\mathbf{u}}}; \quad (1.11)$$

$$\underline{\boldsymbol{\omega}}_{\times} = \underline{\dot{\mathbf{R}}} \cdot \underline{\mathbf{R}}^T; \quad (1.12)$$

which are the velocity vector and gyration tensor respectively. By combining these quantities we can define the time derivative of the Cosserat Strain and Cosserat Wryness under an Eulerian perspective as:

$$\underline{\mathbf{v}} \otimes \underline{\nabla} - \underline{\boldsymbol{\omega}}_{\times}; \quad (1.13)$$

$$\underline{\boldsymbol{\omega}} \otimes \underline{\nabla}; \quad (1.14)$$

By decomposing the gradient of the velocity in its symmetric and skew-symmetric part it is interesting to observe that in case we constrain the material rotation velocity to be equal to the microstructure rotation velocity, the strain recovers its symmetry but the Cosserat theory reduces to an indeterminate continuum mechanics theory, since the skew symmetric part of the stress tensor results to be undefined [14].

Equations 1.10, 1.9, 1.13 and 1.14 are referring to the initial configuration of the media. In Figure 1.2 a schematic representation of the different media configuration is presented. These quantities can be equally evaluated in the Cosserat configuration as well. Features evaluated in the Cosserat configuration are indicated with a sharp sign:

$$\sharp \underline{\mathbf{F}} = \underline{\mathbf{R}}^T \cdot \underline{\mathbf{F}}; \quad (1.15)$$

$$\sharp \underline{\boldsymbol{\Gamma}} = \underline{\mathbf{R}}^T \cdot \underline{\boldsymbol{\Gamma}}; \quad (1.16)$$

$$\sharp \dot{\underline{\mathbf{F}}} \cdot \sharp \underline{\mathbf{F}}^{-1} = \underline{\mathbf{R}}^T \cdot \left[\underline{\mathbf{v}} \otimes \underline{\nabla} - \underline{\boldsymbol{\omega}}_{\times} \right] \cdot \underline{\mathbf{R}}; \quad (1.17)$$

$$\sharp \dot{\underline{\boldsymbol{\Gamma}}} \cdot \sharp \underline{\mathbf{F}}^{-1} = \underline{\mathbf{R}}^T \cdot \left[\underline{\boldsymbol{\omega}} \otimes \underline{\nabla} \right] \cdot \underline{\mathbf{R}}; \quad (1.18)$$

Figure 1.2: Schematic picture of the deformation decomposition in the Cosserat media.

1.3 Balance Laws

To construct the theory of the Cosserat we can start from the definition of the internal power density as function of the quantities whose variations induce an energy variation of the media, that are, the strain rate and the wryness rate defined in Equations 1.13 and 1.14:

$$p^{(i)} = \underline{\underline{\sigma}} : (\underline{\mathbf{v}} \otimes \underline{\nabla} - \underline{\underline{\omega}}_{\times}) + \underline{\underline{\mathbf{m}}} : (\underline{\underline{\omega}} \otimes \underline{\nabla}); \quad (1.19)$$

where $\underline{\underline{\sigma}}$ is the stress tensor, power conjugate to the Cosserat strain rate, and $\underline{\underline{\mathbf{m}}}$ is the couple stress tensor, power conjugate to the Cosserat wryness rate. Note that the stress tensor is in general not symmetric, differently from the stress tensor typically used in classical continuum mechanics.

Equivalently, the densities of power generated by external forces and contact forces can be expressed as:

$$p^{(e)} = \underline{\mathbf{f}}^e \cdot \underline{\mathbf{v}} + \underline{\mathbf{g}}^e \cdot \underline{\underline{\omega}}; \quad (1.20)$$

$$p^{(c)} = \underline{\mathbf{f}}^c \cdot \underline{\mathbf{v}} + \underline{\mathbf{g}}^c \cdot \underline{\underline{\omega}}; \quad (1.21)$$

from which the power balance law can be written as:

$$\int_{\Omega} \underline{\mathbf{v}} \cdot [\underline{\underline{\sigma}} \cdot \underline{\nabla} + \underline{\mathbf{f}}^e] dv + \int_{\partial\Omega} \underline{\mathbf{v}} \cdot [\underline{\mathbf{f}}^c - \underline{\underline{\sigma}} \cdot \underline{\mathbf{n}}] ds + \int_{\Omega} \underline{\underline{\omega}} \cdot [\underline{\underline{\mathbf{m}}} \cdot \underline{\nabla} + 2\underline{\underline{\sigma}}^{\times} + \underline{\mathbf{g}}^e] dv + \int_{\partial\Omega} \underline{\underline{\omega}} \cdot [\underline{\mathbf{g}}^c - \underline{\underline{\mathbf{m}}} \cdot \underline{\mathbf{n}}] ds = 0; \quad (1.22)$$

where $\underline{\mathbf{f}}^e$ is the external volume force, $\underline{\mathbf{g}}^e$ is the external volume couple, $\underline{\mathbf{f}}^c$ is the contact force, $\underline{\mathbf{g}}^c$ is the contact couple, $\underline{\mathbf{n}}$ is the outward normal unit vector of the boundary $\partial\Omega$ which closes the Ω domain and $\underline{\underline{\sigma}}^{\times}$ is the three-components vector obtained from the stress tensor through Equation A.5 containing

the three entries of the skew-symmetric part of the stress tensor. From the balance of power, given the arbitrariness of $\underline{\mathbf{v}}$ and $\underline{\boldsymbol{\omega}}$, the local balance laws can be written for the Cosserat Media:

$$\underline{\boldsymbol{\sigma}} \cdot \underline{\nabla} + \underline{\mathbf{f}}^e = \underline{\mathbf{0}}; \quad (1.23)$$

$$\underline{\mathbf{m}} \cdot \underline{\nabla} + 2\underline{\boldsymbol{\sigma}}^\times + \underline{\mathbf{g}}^e = \underline{\mathbf{0}}; \quad (1.24)$$

which are bounded by the followings:

$$\underline{\boldsymbol{\sigma}} \cdot \underline{\mathbf{n}} = \underline{\mathbf{f}}^c; \quad (1.25)$$

$$\underline{\mathbf{m}} \cdot \underline{\mathbf{n}} = \underline{\mathbf{g}}^c; \quad (1.26)$$

Equation 1.19 expresses the internal power in an Eulerian frame of reference, but we can equivalently express the internal power in a Lagrangian frame of reference. To do so, we need to express the Eulerian quantities in a Lagrangian form. By defining the velocity as $\underline{\mathbf{v}} = \dot{\underline{\mathbf{x}}}$, it is possible to write the deformation gradient rate in a Lagrangian form as:

$$\underline{\mathbf{v}} \otimes \underline{\nabla} = \dot{\underline{\mathbf{F}}} \cdot \underline{\mathbf{F}}^{-1}; \quad (1.27)$$

and, in the same way, we can express the gradient of the pseudovector of microstructure rotation in an Lagrangian form as:

$$\underline{\boldsymbol{\omega}} \otimes \underline{\nabla} = (\underline{\boldsymbol{\omega}} \otimes \underline{\nabla}_0) \cdot \underline{\mathbf{F}}^{-1}; \quad (1.28)$$

Through Equations 1.27 and 1.28, considering that $\underline{\boldsymbol{\sigma}} : \underline{\boldsymbol{\omega}} = 2\underline{\boldsymbol{\sigma}}^\times \cdot \underline{\boldsymbol{\omega}}$, and taking into account density modification, Equation 1.19 transforms into:

$$J p^{(i)} = J \underline{\boldsymbol{\sigma}} \cdot \underline{\mathbf{F}}^{-T} : \dot{\underline{\mathbf{F}}} - 2J \underline{\boldsymbol{\sigma}}^\times \cdot \underline{\boldsymbol{\omega}} + J \underline{\mathbf{m}} \cdot \underline{\mathbf{F}}^{-T} : (\underline{\boldsymbol{\omega}} \otimes \underline{\nabla}_0); \quad (1.29)$$

where we split the stress tensors in the two components that are related to the velocity gradient and the Cosserat rotation tensor. Equation 1.29 can be rewritten as:

$$J p^{(i)} = \underline{\mathbf{S}} : \dot{\underline{\mathbf{F}}} - \underline{\mathbf{s}} \cdot \underline{\boldsymbol{\omega}} + \underline{\mathbf{M}} : (\underline{\boldsymbol{\omega}} \otimes \underline{\nabla}_0); \quad (1.30)$$

from which the power conjugates to $\dot{\underline{\mathbf{F}}}$, $\underline{\boldsymbol{\omega}}$ and $(\underline{\boldsymbol{\omega}} \otimes \underline{\nabla}_0)$ can be clearly identified. It is important to do so since these are the kinematic quantities that are used to write the Cosserat theory in a Lagrangian framework. In particular, we are going to use a description which in classical continuum mechanics would lead to the identification of the two-point *First Piola-Kirchhoff* stress tensor.

Hence, the stress measures in the undertaken approach are:

$$\underline{\mathbf{S}} = J \underline{\boldsymbol{\sigma}} \cdot \underline{\mathbf{F}}^{-T}; \quad (1.31)$$

$$\underline{\mathbf{s}} = 2J \underline{\boldsymbol{\sigma}}^\times; \quad (1.32)$$

$$\underline{\mathbf{M}} = J \underline{\mathbf{m}} \cdot \underline{\mathbf{F}}^{-T}; \quad (1.33)$$

1.4 Constitutive Behavior

A complete description of the constitutive behavior begins with the definition of the Helmholtz free energy, or, in case of isothermal hyper-elastic description, elastic potential. Defining the relation between stress and strain through the elastic potential/Helmholtz free energy definition entails many advantages, for instance, if a potential exists, the fourth-order elastic tensor relating stress and strain benefits from major symmetry.

Starting from the Clausius-Duhem inequality under isothermal condition:

$$-\rho\dot{\psi} + p^{(i)} \geq 0; \quad (1.34)$$

where ρ is the media density and $\dot{\psi}$ is the Helmholtz free energy density rate. By substituting the internal power density:

$$-\rho\dot{\psi} + \underline{\underline{\boldsymbol{\sigma}}} : [\underline{\underline{\mathbf{v}}} \otimes \underline{\underline{\nabla}} - \underline{\underline{\boldsymbol{\omega}}} \times] + \underline{\underline{\mathbf{m}}} : [\underline{\underline{\boldsymbol{\omega}}} \otimes \underline{\underline{\nabla}}]; \quad (1.35)$$

if now we write the Equation above in a Lagrangian framework:

$$-\rho_0\dot{\psi} + \# \underline{\underline{\boldsymbol{\sigma}}} : [\# \underline{\underline{\dot{\mathbf{F}}}} \cdot \# \underline{\underline{\mathbf{F}}}^{-1}] + \# \underline{\underline{\mathbf{m}}} : [\# \underline{\underline{\dot{\mathbf{\Gamma}}}} \cdot \# \underline{\underline{\mathbf{F}}}^{-1}] \geq 0; \quad (1.36)$$

where we identified the power conjugates to the quantities $\# \underline{\underline{\dot{\mathbf{F}}}} \cdot \# \underline{\underline{\mathbf{F}}}^{-1}$ and $\# \underline{\underline{\dot{\mathbf{\Gamma}}}} \cdot \# \underline{\underline{\mathbf{F}}}^{-1}$:

$$\# \underline{\underline{\boldsymbol{\sigma}}} = \mathbf{J} \underline{\underline{\mathbf{R}}}^T \underline{\underline{\boldsymbol{\sigma}}} \underline{\underline{\mathbf{R}}}; \quad (1.37)$$

$$\# \underline{\underline{\mathbf{m}}} = \mathbf{J} \underline{\underline{\mathbf{R}}}^T \underline{\underline{\mathbf{m}}} \underline{\underline{\mathbf{R}}}; \quad (1.38)$$

Furthermore, considering that:

$$\rho_0\dot{\psi} (\# \underline{\underline{\mathbf{F}}}, \# \underline{\underline{\mathbf{\Gamma}}}) = \rho_0 \left[\frac{\partial \psi}{\partial \# \underline{\underline{\mathbf{F}}}} \cdot \# \underline{\underline{\dot{\mathbf{F}}}} + \frac{\partial \psi}{\partial \# \underline{\underline{\mathbf{\Gamma}}}} \cdot \# \underline{\underline{\dot{\mathbf{\Gamma}}}} \right]; \quad (1.39)$$

it is possible to write Equation 1.36 as:

$$\left[-\rho_0 \frac{\partial \psi}{\partial \# \underline{\underline{\mathbf{F}}}} + \# \underline{\underline{\boldsymbol{\sigma}}} \cdot \# \underline{\underline{\mathbf{F}}}^{-T} \right] : \# \underline{\underline{\dot{\mathbf{F}}}} + \left[-\rho_0 \frac{\partial \psi}{\partial \# \underline{\underline{\mathbf{\Gamma}}}} + \# \underline{\underline{\mathbf{m}}} \cdot \# \underline{\underline{\mathbf{F}}}^{-T} \right] : \# \underline{\underline{\dot{\mathbf{\Gamma}}}} \geq 0; \quad (1.40)$$

from which, it can be inferred that:

$$\# \underline{\underline{\boldsymbol{\sigma}}} = \rho_0 \frac{\partial \psi}{\partial \# \underline{\underline{\mathbf{F}}}} \cdot \# \underline{\underline{\mathbf{F}}}^T; \quad (1.41)$$

$$\# \underline{\underline{\mathbf{m}}} = \rho_0 \frac{\partial \psi}{\partial \# \underline{\underline{\mathbf{\Gamma}}}} \cdot \# \underline{\underline{\mathbf{F}}}^T; \quad (1.42)$$

Helmholtz Free Energy Definition

In our work we decided to use the following Helmholtz free energy:

$$\rho\psi (\# \underline{\underline{\mathbf{F}}}, \# \underline{\underline{\mathbf{\Gamma}}}) = \frac{\lambda}{2} (\mathbf{J} - 1)^2 + \mu \|\text{sym} (\# \underline{\underline{\mathbf{F}}}) - \underline{\underline{\mathbf{I}}}\|^2 + \mu_c \|\text{skew} (\# \underline{\underline{\mathbf{F}}} - \underline{\underline{\mathbf{I}}})\|^2 + \frac{\beta}{2} \|\# \underline{\underline{\mathbf{\Gamma}}}\|^2; \quad (1.43)$$

From Equation 1.43 it is evident that it was chosen to define the Helmholtz free energy in the Cosserat configuration. It was possible to define the Helmholtz free energy as function of $\# \underline{\underline{\mathbf{F}}}$ and $\# \underline{\underline{\mathbf{\Gamma}}}$ thanks to the fact that these are objective quantities, i.e. the Cosserat configuration is obtained through an isomorphic transformation (the metric is unchanged).

From Equations 1.43, 1.41 and 1.42, the stress and couple stress in the Cosserat configuration can be written for this specific choice of the Helmholtz free energy:

$$\begin{aligned} \# \underline{\underline{\boldsymbol{\sigma}}} &= \mathbf{J} \lambda (\mathbf{J} - 1) \underline{\underline{\mathbf{I}}} + 2\mu \left(\frac{\# \underline{\underline{\mathbf{F}}} + \# \underline{\underline{\mathbf{F}}}^T}{2} - \underline{\underline{\mathbf{I}}} \right) \cdot \# \underline{\underline{\mathbf{F}}}^T + 2\mu_c \left(\frac{\# \underline{\underline{\mathbf{F}}} - \# \underline{\underline{\mathbf{F}}}^T}{2} \right) \cdot \# \underline{\underline{\mathbf{F}}}^T = \\ &\mathbf{J} \lambda (\mathbf{J} - 1) \underline{\underline{\mathbf{I}}} + (\mu + \mu_c) \left[\underline{\underline{\mathbf{R}}}^T \underline{\underline{\mathbf{F}}} \underline{\underline{\mathbf{F}}}^T \underline{\underline{\mathbf{R}}} \right] + (\mu - \mu_c) \left[\underline{\underline{\mathbf{F}}}^T \underline{\underline{\mathbf{R}}} \underline{\underline{\mathbf{F}}}^T \underline{\underline{\mathbf{R}}} \right] - 2\mu \underline{\underline{\mathbf{F}}}^T \underline{\underline{\mathbf{R}}}; \end{aligned} \quad (1.44)$$

$$\# \underline{\mathbf{m}} = \beta \# \underline{\Gamma} \cdot \# \underline{\mathbf{F}}^T; \quad (1.45)$$

and from the Equations above, the specific form of $\underline{\mathbf{S}}$, $\underline{\mathbf{s}}$ and $\underline{\mathbf{M}}$ can be derived:

$$\underline{\mathbf{S}} = J\lambda(J-1)\underline{\mathbf{F}}^{-T} + \mu \left(\underline{\mathbf{F}} + \underline{\mathbf{R}} \cdot \underline{\mathbf{F}}^T \cdot \underline{\mathbf{R}} - 2\underline{\mathbf{R}} \right) + \mu_c \left(\underline{\mathbf{F}} - \underline{\mathbf{R}} \cdot \underline{\mathbf{F}}^T \cdot \underline{\mathbf{R}} \right); \quad (1.46)$$

$$\underline{\mathbf{s}} = -\underline{\epsilon} : \left(\underline{\mathbf{S}} \cdot \underline{\mathbf{F}}^T \right); \quad (1.47)$$

$$\underline{\mathbf{M}} = \beta \underline{\Gamma} \quad (1.48)$$

1.5 Problem Discretization

The discretization procedure starts with the discretization of the entire domain of interest Ω in n sub-domains, which are commonly referred to as mesh *elements*. We can write for the internal power for example:

$$\int_{\Omega} p^{(i)} d\Omega = \sum_i^n \int_{\Omega_i} p^{(i)}, \quad \Omega_i \cap \Omega_j = 0, \forall i \neq j, \quad \bigcup_i^n \Omega_i = \Omega; \quad (1.49)$$

to be noted that the one above is not an approximation. Successively, we can define a discrete number of point for each of these sub-domains that are referred to as *nodes*. The purpose of the nodes is to embody field informations in a discrete number of locations rather than in the whole continuum. The values of the fields between the nodes is subsequently approximated through interpolating functions. In this step the finite element approximation is performed by discretizing the continuum's degrees of freedom as:

$$\underline{\mathbf{u}}(x, y, z) = \underline{\mathbf{N}}^u(x, y, z) \cdot \underline{\chi}^u; \quad (1.50)$$

$$\underline{\boldsymbol{\theta}}(x, y, z) = \underline{\mathbf{N}}^\theta(x, y, z) \cdot \underline{\chi}^\theta; \quad (1.51)$$

where $\underline{\chi}^u$ and $\underline{\chi}^\theta$ are the vectors containing the displacement and rotational degrees of freedom respectively, and $\underline{\mathbf{N}}^u$ and $\underline{\mathbf{N}}^\theta$ are the matrices containing the shape functions of the displacement and rotations respectively. Furthermore, by defining:

$$\underline{\mathbf{B}}^u = \underline{\mathbf{N}}^u \otimes \underline{\nabla}; \quad (1.52)$$

$$\underline{\mathbf{B}}^\theta = \underline{\mathbf{N}}^\theta \otimes \underline{\nabla}; \quad (1.53)$$

we are able to evaluate the gradient of the displacement and rotational fields as:

$$\underline{\mathbf{v}} \otimes \underline{\nabla}_0 = \underline{\mathbf{B}}^u \cdot \underline{\dot{\chi}}^u; \quad (1.54)$$

$$\underline{\boldsymbol{\omega}} \otimes \underline{\nabla}_0 = \underline{\mathbf{B}}^\theta \cdot \underline{\dot{\chi}}^\theta; \quad (1.55)$$

$$(1.56)$$

The virtual power principle states that if a configuration of the media \mathcal{C}_t is in equilibrium under a system of external forces, then the virtual power produced by a virtual rate of perturbation of the degrees of freedom of the continuum (the virtual variations must be compatible with the constraints) must be null. Our purpose is to propose the formulation of the virtual power equation in a Finite Element domain description. It is possible to do so through the discretization previously performed. Equation 1.30 expresses the internal power by mean of equivalent first Piola-Kirchhoff stress measures and respective conjugate deformation measures, and the integration is performed in the reference configuration, that is, the original domain occupied by the body. Before doing so, it is required that, to facilitate the

implementation of this theory in a FEM environment, **second and third order matrices will be handles as first and second order matrices respectively as follows:**

$$\underline{\underline{\mathbf{B}}} \Rightarrow \underline{\underline{\mathbf{B}}}; \quad (1.57)$$

$$\underline{\underline{\mathbf{S}}} \Rightarrow \underline{\underline{\mathbf{S}}}; \quad (1.58)$$

$$\underline{\underline{\mathbf{M}}} \Rightarrow \underline{\underline{\mathbf{M}}}; \quad (1.59)$$

$$\underline{\underline{\mathbf{F}}} \Rightarrow \underline{\underline{\mathbf{F}}}; \quad (1.60)$$

$$\underline{\underline{\boldsymbol{\omega}}} \otimes \underline{\underline{\boldsymbol{\nabla}}}_0 \Rightarrow \underline{\underline{\boldsymbol{\omega}}} \otimes \underline{\underline{\boldsymbol{\nabla}}}_0; \quad (1.61)$$

and this is achievable by establishing an unique mapping between different order tensors according to which the tensor entries must be re-distributed. By discretizing the internal power as previously covered we can write:

$$P^{(i)} = \int_{\Omega_i} \left(\underline{\underline{\mathbf{S}}} \cdot \underline{\underline{\dot{\mathbf{F}}}} - \underline{\underline{\mathbf{s}}} \cdot \underline{\underline{\boldsymbol{\omega}}} + \underline{\underline{\mathbf{M}}} \cdot \underline{\underline{\boldsymbol{\omega}}} \otimes \underline{\underline{\boldsymbol{\nabla}}}_0 \right) d\Omega \quad (1.62)$$

which can then be discretized as:

$$P^{(i)} \approx \left[\int_{\Omega_i} \left(\underline{\underline{\mathbf{S}}} \cdot \underline{\underline{\mathbf{B}}}^u \right) d\Omega \right] \cdot \underline{\underline{\dot{\mathbf{x}}}}^u + \left[\int_{\Omega_i} \left(\underline{\underline{\mathbf{M}}} \cdot \underline{\underline{\mathbf{B}}}^\theta - \underline{\underline{\mathbf{s}}} \cdot \underline{\underline{\mathbf{N}}}^{\theta \times} \right) d\Omega \right] \cdot \underline{\underline{\dot{\mathbf{x}}}}^\theta; \quad (1.63)$$

where the integration must be performed in the reference (initial) configuration, i.e. following the Lagrangian approach. Accordingly, assuming that the external forces are only contact forces, from Equation 1.21 the external virtual power can be discretized as:

$$P^{(e)} \approx \left[\int_{\partial\Omega_i} \left(\underline{\underline{\mathbf{f}}}^c \cdot \underline{\underline{\mathbf{N}}}^u \right) dS \right] \cdot \underline{\underline{\dot{\mathbf{x}}}}^u + \left[\int_{\partial\Omega_i} \left(\underline{\underline{\mathbf{g}}}^c \cdot \underline{\underline{\mathbf{N}}}^\theta \right) dS \right] \cdot \underline{\underline{\dot{\mathbf{x}}}}^\theta; \quad (1.64)$$

from which, the discretized power balance equation looks like:

$$\left[\int_{\Omega_i} \left(\underline{\underline{\mathbf{S}}} \cdot \underline{\underline{\mathbf{B}}}^u \right) d\Omega \right] \cdot \underline{\underline{\dot{\mathbf{x}}}}^u + \left[\int_{\Omega_i} \left(\underline{\underline{\mathbf{M}}} \cdot \underline{\underline{\mathbf{B}}}^\theta - \underline{\underline{\mathbf{s}}} \cdot \underline{\underline{\mathbf{N}}}^\theta \right) d\Omega \right] \cdot \underline{\underline{\dot{\mathbf{x}}}}^\theta = \left[\int_{\partial\Omega_i} \left(\underline{\underline{\mathbf{f}}}^c \cdot \underline{\underline{\mathbf{N}}}^u \right) dS \right] \cdot \underline{\underline{\dot{\mathbf{x}}}}^u + \left[\int_{\partial\Omega_i} \left(\underline{\underline{\mathbf{g}}}^c \cdot \underline{\underline{\mathbf{N}}}^\theta \right) dS \right] \cdot \underline{\underline{\dot{\mathbf{x}}}}^\theta; \quad (1.65)$$

and given the arbitrariness of the virtual rates of the nodal degrees of freedom, is it possible to elide them from the Equations, which would then transform into a balance Equation between the internal an external forces:

$$\underline{\underline{\mathbf{f}}}_{\text{int}} = \underline{\underline{\mathbf{f}}}_{\text{ext}} \Rightarrow \begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{f}_{\text{int}1}^{u1} \\ \mathbf{f}_{\text{int}2}^{u1} \\ \vdots \\ \mathbf{f}_{\text{int}n}^{un} \\ \mathbf{f}_{\text{int}1}^{\theta1} \\ \mathbf{f}_{\text{int}2}^{\theta1} \\ \vdots \\ \mathbf{f}_{\text{int}n}^{\theta n} \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{f}_{\text{ext}1}^{u1} \\ \mathbf{f}_{\text{ext}2}^{u1} \\ \vdots \\ \mathbf{f}_{\text{ext}n}^{un} \\ \mathbf{f}_{\text{ext}1}^{\theta1} \\ \mathbf{f}_{\text{ext}2}^{\theta1} \\ \vdots \\ \mathbf{f}_{\text{ext}n}^{\theta n} \end{bmatrix} \Rightarrow \begin{bmatrix} \int_{\Omega_i} \left(\underline{\underline{\mathbf{B}}}^{uT} \cdot \underline{\underline{\mathbf{S}}} \right) d\Omega \\ \int_{\Omega_i} \left(\underline{\underline{\mathbf{B}}}^{\theta T} \cdot \underline{\underline{\mathbf{M}}} - \underline{\underline{\mathbf{N}}}^{\theta T} \cdot \underline{\underline{\mathbf{s}}} \right) d\Omega \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} \int_{\partial\Omega_i} \left(\underline{\underline{\mathbf{N}}}^{uT} \cdot \underline{\underline{\mathbf{f}}}^c \right) dS \\ \int_{\partial\Omega_i} \left(\underline{\underline{\mathbf{N}}}^{\theta T} \cdot \underline{\underline{\mathbf{g}}}^c \right) dS \end{bmatrix} \quad (1.66)$$

where the subscripts and superscripts of the forces indicate the number of the node and the type of degree of freedom respectively. Some transposes appeared in the formulation to retain matrix multiplication compatibility. The Equilibrium condition imposed by Equation 1.67 must be verified at every point of the

load-path. Assuming the configuration of the continuum as known at a generic time t , and hypothesizing that the external force does not depend on the d.o.f. variation, the internal force at time $t + \Delta t$ can be thought as derived from the continuum condition at time t , and the equilibrium condition can be written as:

$$\underline{\mathbf{f}}_{\text{int}}^{t+\Delta t} \approx \frac{\partial \underline{\mathbf{f}}_{\text{int}}^t(\underline{\chi}^t)}{\partial \underline{\chi}} \cdot \underline{\delta \chi} = \underline{\mathbf{K}}^t \cdot \underline{\delta \chi} = \underline{\mathbf{f}}_{\text{ext}}^{t+\Delta t}; \quad (1.67)$$

where $\underline{\mathbf{K}}^t$ is the element stiffness matrix evaluated at time t , representing nothing but a linear perturbation of the internal forces with respect to the variation nodal degrees of freedom. In order to write Equation 1.67 in a consistent way, the $\underline{\mathbf{K}}$ matrix has the following entries:

$$\underline{\mathbf{K}} = \begin{bmatrix} \frac{\partial f_{\text{int}_1}^u}{\partial u_1^1} & \frac{\partial f_{\text{int}_1}^u}{\partial u_1^2} & \frac{\partial f_{\text{int}_1}^u}{\partial u_1^3} & \cdots & \frac{\partial f_{\text{int}_1}^u}{\partial u_n^3} & \frac{\partial f_{\text{int}_1}^u}{\partial \theta_1^1} & \frac{\partial f_{\text{int}_1}^u}{\partial \theta_1^2} & \cdots & \frac{\partial f_{\text{int}_1}^u}{\partial \theta_n^3} \\ \vdots & \vdots \\ \frac{\partial f_{\text{int}_n}^u}{\partial u_1^1} & \frac{\partial f_{\text{int}_n}^u}{\partial u_1^2} & \frac{\partial f_{\text{int}_n}^u}{\partial u_1^3} & \cdots & \frac{\partial f_{\text{int}_n}^u}{\partial u_n^3} & \frac{\partial f_{\text{int}_n}^u}{\partial \theta_1^1} & \frac{\partial f_{\text{int}_n}^u}{\partial \theta_1^2} & \cdots & \frac{\partial f_{\text{int}_n}^u}{\partial \theta_n^3} \\ \frac{\partial f_{\text{int}_1}^\theta}{\partial u_n^1} & \frac{\partial f_{\text{int}_1}^\theta}{\partial u_1^2} & \frac{\partial f_{\text{int}_1}^\theta}{\partial u_1^3} & \cdots & \frac{\partial f_{\text{int}_1}^\theta}{\partial u_n^3} & \frac{\partial f_{\text{int}_1}^\theta}{\partial \theta_1^1} & \frac{\partial f_{\text{int}_1}^\theta}{\partial \theta_1^2} & \cdots & \frac{\partial f_{\text{int}_1}^\theta}{\partial \theta_n^3} \\ \vdots & \vdots \\ \frac{\partial f_{\text{int}_n}^\theta}{\partial u_n^1} & \frac{\partial f_{\text{int}_n}^\theta}{\partial u_1^2} & \frac{\partial f_{\text{int}_n}^\theta}{\partial u_1^3} & \cdots & \frac{\partial f_{\text{int}_n}^\theta}{\partial u_n^3} & \frac{\partial f_{\text{int}_n}^\theta}{\partial \theta_1^1} & \frac{\partial f_{\text{int}_n}^\theta}{\partial \theta_1^2} & \cdots & \frac{\partial f_{\text{int}_n}^\theta}{\partial \theta_n^3} \end{bmatrix} \quad (1.68)$$

which can also be re-written as:

$$\underline{\mathbf{K}} = \begin{bmatrix} \int_{\Omega_i} \left(\underline{\mathbf{B}}^{u^T} \cdot \frac{\partial \underline{\mathbf{S}}}{\partial \underline{\chi}^u} \right) d\Omega & \int_{\Omega_i} \left(\underline{\mathbf{B}}^{u^T} \cdot \frac{\partial \underline{\mathbf{S}}}{\partial \underline{\chi}^\theta} \right) d\Omega \\ \int_{\Omega_i} \left(\underline{\mathbf{B}}^{\theta^T} \cdot \frac{\partial \underline{\mathbf{M}}}{\partial \underline{\chi}^u} - \underline{\mathbf{N}}^{\theta^T} \cdot \frac{\partial \underline{\mathbf{s}}}{\partial \underline{\chi}^u} \right) d\Omega & \int_{\Omega_i} \left(\underline{\mathbf{B}}^{\theta^T} \cdot \frac{\partial \underline{\mathbf{M}}}{\partial \underline{\chi}^\theta} - \underline{\mathbf{N}}^{\theta^T} \cdot \frac{\partial \underline{\mathbf{s}}}{\partial \underline{\chi}^\theta} \right) d\Omega \end{bmatrix} \quad (1.69)$$

where the four sub-matrices composing the stiffness matrix can be clearly identified. Note that the variations of the B matrices are null because we are under using a Lagrangian approach. In the classical continuum mechanics only the top-left part of the matrix is used. The entries of the stiffness matrix can be easily evaluated considering that the fluxes do not directly depend on the degrees of freedom, rather on the continuum deformation measures ($\underline{\mathbf{F}}(\underline{\mathbf{u}}), \underline{\mathbf{R}}(\underline{\theta}), \underline{\Gamma}(\underline{\theta})$), so it is possible to apply the product rule:

$$\frac{\partial \underline{\mathbf{S}}}{\partial \underline{\chi}^u} = \frac{\partial \underline{\mathbf{S}}}{\partial \underline{\mathbf{F}}} \cdot \frac{\partial \underline{\mathbf{F}}}{\partial \underline{\chi}^u} = \frac{\partial \underline{\mathbf{S}}}{\partial \underline{\mathbf{F}}} \cdot \underline{\mathbf{B}}^u \iff \frac{\partial S_i}{\partial \chi_j^u} = \frac{\partial S_i}{\partial F_k} \frac{\partial F_k}{\partial \chi_j^u} = \frac{\partial S_i}{\partial F_k} B_{kj}^u \quad (1.70)$$

$$\frac{\partial \underline{\mathbf{S}}}{\partial \underline{\chi}^\theta} = \frac{\partial \underline{\mathbf{S}}}{\partial \underline{\mathbf{R}}} \cdot \frac{\partial \underline{\mathbf{R}}}{\partial \underline{\chi}^\theta} + \frac{\partial \underline{\mathbf{S}}}{\partial \underline{\Gamma}} \cdot \frac{\partial \underline{\Gamma}}{\partial \underline{\chi}^\theta} \iff \frac{\partial S_i}{\partial \chi_j^\theta} = \frac{\partial S_i}{\partial R_k} \frac{\partial R_k}{\partial \chi_j^\theta} + \frac{\partial S_i}{\partial \Gamma_k} \frac{\partial \Gamma_k}{\partial \chi_j^\theta} \quad (1.71)$$

$$\frac{\partial \underline{\mathbf{M}}}{\partial \underline{\chi}^u} = \frac{\partial \underline{\mathbf{M}}}{\partial \underline{\mathbf{F}}} \cdot \frac{\partial \underline{\mathbf{F}}}{\partial \underline{\chi}^u} = \frac{\partial \underline{\mathbf{M}}}{\partial \underline{\mathbf{F}}} \cdot \underline{\mathbf{B}}^u \iff \frac{\partial M_i}{\partial \chi_j^u} = \frac{\partial M_i}{\partial F_k} \frac{\partial F_k}{\partial \chi_j^u} = \frac{\partial M_i}{\partial F_k} B_{kj}^u \quad (1.72)$$

$$\frac{\partial \underline{\mathbf{M}}}{\partial \underline{\chi}^\theta} = \frac{\partial \underline{\mathbf{M}}}{\partial \underline{\mathbf{R}}} \cdot \frac{\partial \underline{\mathbf{R}}}{\partial \underline{\chi}^\theta} + \frac{\partial \underline{\mathbf{M}}}{\partial \underline{\Gamma}} \cdot \frac{\partial \underline{\Gamma}}{\partial \underline{\chi}^\theta} \iff \frac{\partial M_i}{\partial \chi_j^\theta} = \frac{\partial M_i}{\partial R_k} \frac{\partial R_k}{\partial \chi_j^\theta} + \frac{\partial M_i}{\partial \Gamma_k} \frac{\partial \Gamma_k}{\partial \chi_j^\theta} \quad (1.73)$$

$$\frac{\partial \underline{\mathbf{s}}}{\partial \underline{\chi}^u} = \frac{\partial \underline{\mathbf{s}}}{\partial \underline{\mathbf{F}}} \cdot \frac{\partial \underline{\mathbf{F}}}{\partial \underline{\chi}^u} = \frac{\partial \underline{\mathbf{s}}}{\partial \underline{\mathbf{F}}} \cdot \underline{\mathbf{B}}^u \iff \frac{\partial s_i}{\partial \chi_j^u} = \frac{\partial s_i}{\partial F_k} \frac{\partial F_k}{\partial \chi_j^u} = \frac{\partial s_i}{\partial F_k} B_{kj}^u \quad (1.74)$$

$$\frac{\partial \underline{\mathbf{s}}}{\partial \underline{\chi}^\theta} = \frac{\partial \underline{\mathbf{s}}}{\partial \underline{\mathbf{R}}} \cdot \frac{\partial \underline{\mathbf{R}}}{\partial \underline{\chi}^\theta} + \frac{\partial \underline{\mathbf{s}}}{\partial \underline{\Gamma}} \cdot \frac{\partial \underline{\Gamma}}{\partial \underline{\chi}^\theta} \iff \frac{\partial s_i}{\partial \chi_j^\theta} = \frac{\partial s_i}{\partial R_k} \frac{\partial R_k}{\partial \chi_j^\theta} + \frac{\partial s_i}{\partial \Gamma_k} \frac{\partial \Gamma_k}{\partial \chi_j^\theta} \quad (1.75)$$

The variations of the fluxes with respect to the deformation measures correspond to the entries of the material tangent matrix, and they will be evaluated in the following section. With the development of the terms just presented, the element tangent matrix in Equation 1.69 can be rewritten as:

$$\underline{\underline{\mathbf{K}}} = \left[\begin{array}{c|c} \int_{\Omega_i} \left(\underline{\underline{\mathbf{B}}}^{u^T} \cdot \frac{\partial \underline{\underline{\mathbf{S}}}}{\partial \underline{\underline{\mathbf{F}}}} \cdot \underline{\underline{\mathbf{B}}}^u \right) d\Omega & \int_{\Omega_i} \left[\underline{\underline{\mathbf{B}}}^{u^T} \cdot \left(\frac{\partial \underline{\underline{\mathbf{S}}}}{\partial \underline{\underline{\mathbf{R}}}} \cdot \frac{\partial \underline{\underline{\mathbf{R}}}}{\partial \underline{\underline{\chi}}^\theta} + \frac{\partial \underline{\underline{\mathbf{S}}}}{\partial \underline{\underline{\Gamma}}} \cdot \frac{\partial \underline{\underline{\Gamma}}}{\partial \underline{\underline{\chi}}^\theta} \right) \right] d\Omega \\ \hline \int_{\Omega_i} \left(\underline{\underline{\mathbf{B}}}^{\theta^T} \cdot \frac{\partial \underline{\underline{\mathbf{M}}}}{\partial \underline{\underline{\mathbf{F}}}} \cdot \underline{\underline{\mathbf{B}}}^u - \underline{\underline{\mathbf{N}}}^{\theta^T} \cdot \frac{\partial \underline{\underline{\mathbf{s}}}}{\partial \underline{\underline{\mathbf{F}}}} \cdot \underline{\underline{\mathbf{B}}}^u \right) d\Omega & \int_{\Omega_i} \left[\underline{\underline{\mathbf{B}}}^{\theta^T} \cdot \left(\frac{\partial \underline{\underline{\mathbf{M}}}}{\partial \underline{\underline{\mathbf{R}}}} \cdot \frac{\partial \underline{\underline{\mathbf{R}}}}{\partial \underline{\underline{\chi}}^\theta} + \frac{\partial \underline{\underline{\mathbf{M}}}}{\partial \underline{\underline{\Gamma}}} \cdot \frac{\partial \underline{\underline{\Gamma}}}{\partial \underline{\underline{\chi}}^\theta} \right) - \underline{\underline{\mathbf{N}}}^{\theta^T} \cdot \left(\frac{\partial \underline{\underline{\mathbf{s}}}}{\partial \underline{\underline{\mathbf{R}}}} \cdot \frac{\partial \underline{\underline{\mathbf{R}}}}{\partial \underline{\underline{\chi}}^\theta} + \frac{\partial \underline{\underline{\mathbf{s}}}}{\partial \underline{\underline{\Gamma}}} \cdot \frac{\partial \underline{\underline{\Gamma}}}{\partial \underline{\underline{\chi}}^\theta} \right) \right] d\Omega \end{array} \right] \quad (1.76)$$

Regarding the external forces vector, the boundary conditions in Equations 1.25 and 1.26 can be used to transform the contact force and contact moment vectors, then the divergence theorem must be applied and then finally the resulting Equation can be transformed from Eulerian to Lagrangian resulting in the followings:

$$\int_{\partial\Omega_i} \left(\underline{\underline{\mathbf{N}}}^{u^T} \cdot \underline{\underline{\mathbf{f}}}^c \right) dS = \int_{\Omega_i} \left(\underline{\underline{\mathbf{B}}}^{u^T} \cdot \underline{\underline{\mathbf{S}}} \right) d\Omega; \quad (1.77)$$

$$\int_{\partial\Omega_i} \left(\underline{\underline{\mathbf{N}}}^{\theta^T} \cdot \underline{\underline{\mathbf{g}}}^c \right) dS = \int_{\Omega_i} \left(\underline{\underline{\mathbf{B}}}^{\theta^T} \cdot \underline{\underline{\mathbf{M}}} \right) d\Omega - \int_{\Omega_i} \left(\underline{\underline{\mathbf{N}}}^{\theta^T} \cdot \underline{\underline{\mathbf{s}}} \right) d\Omega; \quad (1.78)$$

To implement the element stiffness matrix, the variation of the deformations at the IP with respect to the nodal degrees of freedom must be evaluated, alongside the material tangent matrix.

1.6 Constructing the Material Tangent Matrix

In Equation 1.76 the terms expressing the variation of the fluxes at the IP with respect to the deformation measure and the terms relating the variation of the deformation measure to nodal perturbation of the degrees of freedom require further development. The first group is nothing but the material tangent matrix:

$$\underline{\underline{\mathbf{K}}}_M = \frac{\partial(\underline{\underline{\mathbf{flux}}})}{\partial(\underline{\underline{\mathbf{def}}})} \iff M_{ijkl} = \frac{\partial(\underline{\underline{\mathbf{flux}}})_{ij}}{\partial(\underline{\underline{\mathbf{def}}})_{kl}}; \quad (1.79)$$

where the fluxes are:

$$\underline{\underline{\mathbf{flux}}} = \{ \underline{\underline{\mathbf{S}}}, \underline{\underline{\mathbf{s}}}, \underline{\underline{\mathbf{M}}} \}; \quad (1.80)$$

and the deformations are:

$$\underline{\underline{\mathbf{def}}} = \{ \underline{\underline{\mathbf{F}}}, \underline{\underline{\mathbf{R}}}, \underline{\underline{\Gamma}} \}; \quad (1.81)$$

and if we imagine of re-arranging second order tensor into first order tensors, we can write the material tangent matrix as:

$$\underline{\underline{\mathbf{K}}}_M = \frac{\partial(\underline{\underline{\mathbf{flux}}})}{\partial(\underline{\underline{\mathbf{def}}})} \iff M_{ij} = \frac{\partial(\underline{\underline{\mathbf{flux}}})_i}{\partial(\underline{\underline{\mathbf{def}}})_j}; \quad (1.82)$$

and the matrix would be composed as:

$$\underline{\underline{\mathbf{K}}}_M = \begin{bmatrix} \frac{\partial \underline{\mathbf{S}}}{\partial \underline{\mathbf{F}}} & \frac{\partial \underline{\mathbf{S}}}{\partial \underline{\mathbf{R}}} & \underline{\underline{\mathbf{0}}} \\ \frac{\partial \underline{\mathbf{s}}}{\partial \underline{\mathbf{F}}} & \frac{\partial \underline{\mathbf{s}}}{\partial \underline{\mathbf{R}}} & \underline{\underline{\mathbf{0}}} \\ \underline{\underline{\mathbf{0}}} & \underline{\underline{\mathbf{0}}} & \frac{\partial \underline{\mathbf{M}}}{\partial \underline{\mathbf{\Gamma}}} \end{bmatrix} \quad (1.83)$$

the entries of the material tangent matrix will be evaluated assuming the plane strain condition, since this constrain sensitively simplifies the derivation.

1.6.1 Consequences of the Plane Strain assumption

Given a generic rotation matrix as:

$$\underline{\underline{\mathbf{R}}} = \exp(-\underline{\underline{\boldsymbol{\epsilon}}} \cdot \underline{\underline{\boldsymbol{\omega}}}); \quad (1.84)$$

if the rotation vector has only one non-zero component (simple rotation around one of the axis), for example θ_0 around the z-axis, it can be written as:

$$\underline{\underline{\mathbf{R}}} = \exp\left(-\underline{\underline{\boldsymbol{\epsilon}}} \cdot \begin{bmatrix} 0 \\ 0 \\ \theta_0 \end{bmatrix}\right) = \exp\left(0 \begin{bmatrix} 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & -1 \\ 0 & 1 & 0 \end{bmatrix} + 0 \begin{bmatrix} 0 & 0 & 1 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 \\ -1 & 0 & 0 \end{bmatrix} + \theta_0 \begin{bmatrix} 0 & -1 & 0 \\ 1 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 \end{bmatrix}\right) = \exp(\theta_0 \underline{\underline{\mathbf{A}}}); \quad (1.85)$$

which, in case we need its variation w.r.t. the rotation vector, can be simply derived with respect to θ_0 obtaining:

$$\frac{\partial \underline{\underline{\mathbf{R}}}}{\partial \theta_0} = \underline{\underline{\mathbf{A}}} \cdot \underline{\underline{\mathbf{R}}} = \underline{\underline{\mathbf{R}}}' ; \quad (1.86)$$

$$\frac{\partial \underline{\underline{\mathbf{R}}}' }{\partial \theta_0} = \underline{\underline{\mathbf{A}}} \cdot \underline{\underline{\mathbf{R}}}' = \underline{\underline{\mathbf{R}}}' ; \quad (1.87)$$

furthermore, the gradient of $\underline{\underline{\mathbf{R}}}$ and $\underline{\underline{\mathbf{R}}}'$ can be evaluated as:

$$\underline{\underline{\mathbf{R}}} \otimes \underline{\underline{\nabla}}_0 \iff \frac{\partial R_{ij}}{\partial X_k} = \frac{\partial R_{ij}}{\partial \theta_0} \frac{\partial \theta_0}{\partial X_k} = R'_{ij} B_{kl}^{\otimes} \chi_l^{\otimes} \quad (1.88)$$

$$\underline{\underline{\mathbf{R}}}' \otimes \underline{\underline{\nabla}}_0 \iff \frac{\partial R'_{ij}}{\partial X_k} = \frac{\partial R'_{ij}}{\partial \theta_0} \frac{\partial \theta_0}{\partial X_k} = R''_{ij} B_{kl}^{\otimes} \chi_l^{\otimes} \quad (1.89)$$

therefore:

$$\underline{\underline{\mathbf{R}}} \otimes \underline{\underline{\nabla}}_0 = \underline{\underline{\mathbf{R}}}' \otimes \left(\underline{\underline{\mathbf{B}}}^{\otimes} \cdot \underline{\underline{\boldsymbol{\chi}}}^{\otimes}\right); \quad (1.90)$$

$$\underline{\underline{\mathbf{R}}}' \otimes \underline{\underline{\nabla}}_0 = \underline{\underline{\mathbf{A}}} \cdot \underline{\underline{\mathbf{R}}}' \otimes \left(\underline{\underline{\mathbf{B}}}^{\otimes} \cdot \underline{\underline{\boldsymbol{\chi}}}^{\otimes}\right) = \underline{\underline{\mathbf{R}}}' \otimes \left(\underline{\underline{\mathbf{B}}}^{\otimes} \cdot \underline{\underline{\boldsymbol{\chi}}}^{\otimes}\right); \quad (1.91)$$

and equivalently:

$$\underline{\mathbf{R}}^T \otimes \underline{\mathbf{V}}_0 = \underline{\mathbf{R}}'^T \otimes \left(\underline{\mathbf{B}}^{\times\theta} \cdot \underline{\mathbf{X}}^{\times\theta} \right); \quad (1.92)$$

$$\underline{\mathbf{R}}'^T \otimes \underline{\mathbf{V}}_0 = \underline{\mathbf{R}}''^T \otimes \left(\underline{\mathbf{B}}^{\times\theta} \cdot \underline{\mathbf{X}}^{\times\theta} \right); \quad (1.93)$$

Under the same simplifying assumption, it is also possible to evaluate the derivative of the wryness with respect to the rotation θ^0 :

$$\frac{\underline{\mathbf{\Gamma}}}{\partial\theta^0} = \underline{\mathbf{\Gamma}}' = \frac{1}{2} \underline{\boldsymbol{\epsilon}} : \left[\frac{\partial \underline{\mathbf{R}}}{\partial\theta^0} \cdot \left(\underline{\mathbf{R}}^T \otimes \underline{\mathbf{V}}_0 \right) + \underline{\mathbf{R}} \cdot \left(\frac{\partial \underline{\mathbf{R}}^T}{\partial\theta^0} \otimes \underline{\mathbf{V}}_0 \right) \right]; \quad (1.94)$$

Given the assumption of bi-dimensionality, the only active components of the wryness tensor are the ones related to the variation of the rotation angle θ^3 along the x and y direction, i.e. Γ_{31} and Γ_{32} :

$$\underline{\mathbf{\Gamma}} = \begin{bmatrix} 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 \\ \Gamma_{31} & \Gamma_{32} & 0 \end{bmatrix} \quad (1.95)$$

Furthermore, it can be demonstrated that under plane strain conditions:

$$\underline{\mathbf{\Gamma}} = \begin{bmatrix} \Gamma_1 \\ \Gamma_2 \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} \frac{\partial\theta^3}{\partial X_1} \\ \frac{\partial\theta^3}{\partial X_2} \end{bmatrix} = \underline{\mathbf{B}}^{\theta} \cdot \underline{\mathbf{X}}^{\theta}; \quad (1.96)$$

From these simplifications, it is possible to compose the material tangent matrix, which can be written as:

$$\underline{\underline{\mathbf{K}}}_M = \frac{\partial(\underline{\mathbf{flux}})}{\partial(\underline{\mathbf{def}})} \iff K_{M_{ijkl}} = \frac{\partial(\underline{\mathbf{flux}})_{ij}}{\partial(\underline{\mathbf{def}})_{kl}}; \quad (1.97)$$

where, under the assumption we made, the fluxes are:

$$\underline{\mathbf{flux}} = \{ \underline{\mathbf{S}}, s_3, \underline{\mathbf{M}} \}; \quad (1.98)$$

and the deformations are:

$$\underline{\mathbf{def}} = \{ \underline{\mathbf{F}}, \theta^3, \underline{\mathbf{\Gamma}} \}; \quad (1.99)$$

where the $\underline{\mathbf{M}}$ vector and the $\underline{\mathbf{\Gamma}}$ vectors only contain the components $\{M_{31}, M_{32}\}$ and $\{\Gamma_{31}, \Gamma_{32}\}$ respectively. It is important to note here that we used the degree of freedom θ^3 itself as a measure of deformation rather than the rotation matrix;. Although this simplifies the equations, we have to include the term $\underline{\mathbf{R}}'$ in the material tangent matrix to preserve consistency, therefore, by using the result of Equations 1.86 and 1.94 it is possible to write:

$$\frac{\partial \underline{\mathbf{S}}}{\partial \underline{\mathbf{X}}^{\times\theta}} = \frac{\partial \underline{\mathbf{S}}}{\partial \theta^3} \otimes \frac{\partial \theta^3}{\partial \underline{\mathbf{X}}^{\times\theta}} = \frac{\partial \underline{\mathbf{S}}}{\partial \underline{\mathbf{R}}} \cdot \frac{\partial \underline{\mathbf{R}}}{\partial \theta^3} \otimes \frac{\partial \theta^3}{\partial \underline{\mathbf{X}}^{\times\theta}} = \frac{\partial \underline{\mathbf{S}}}{\partial \underline{\mathbf{R}}} \cdot \underline{\mathbf{R}}' \otimes \underline{\mathbf{N}}^{\times\theta}; \quad (1.100)$$

$$\frac{\partial s_3}{\partial \underline{\mathbf{X}}^{\times\theta}} = \frac{\partial s_3}{\partial \theta^3} \otimes \frac{\partial \theta^3}{\partial \underline{\mathbf{X}}^{\times\theta}} = \frac{\partial s_3}{\partial \underline{\mathbf{R}}} \cdot \frac{\partial \underline{\mathbf{R}}}{\partial \theta^3} \otimes \frac{\partial \theta^3}{\partial \underline{\mathbf{X}}^{\times\theta}} = \frac{\partial s_3}{\partial \underline{\mathbf{R}}} \cdot \underline{\mathbf{R}}' \otimes \underline{\mathbf{N}}^{\times\theta}; \quad (1.101)$$

$$\frac{\partial \underline{\mathbf{M}}}{\partial \underline{\mathbf{X}}^{\times\theta}} = \frac{\partial \underline{\mathbf{M}}}{\partial \theta^3} \otimes \frac{\partial \theta^3}{\partial \underline{\mathbf{X}}^{\times\theta}} = \frac{\partial \underline{\mathbf{M}}}{\partial \underline{\mathbf{\Gamma}}} \cdot \frac{\partial \underline{\mathbf{\Gamma}}}{\partial \theta^3} \otimes \frac{\partial \theta^3}{\partial \underline{\mathbf{X}}^{\times\theta}} = \frac{\partial \underline{\mathbf{M}}}{\partial \underline{\mathbf{\Gamma}}} \cdot \frac{\partial \underline{\mathbf{\Gamma}}}{\partial \underline{\mathbf{X}}^{\times\theta}} = \frac{\partial \underline{\mathbf{M}}}{\partial \underline{\mathbf{\Gamma}}} \cdot \underline{\mathbf{B}}^{\times\theta}; \quad (1.102)$$

If we once again handle second order tensors as properly-ordered first order tensors, we can re-write the material tangent matrix as:

$$\underline{\underline{\mathbf{K}}}_M = \frac{\partial(\underline{\mathbf{flux}})}{\partial(\underline{\mathbf{def}})} \iff K_{M_{ijkl}} = \frac{\partial(\underline{\mathbf{flux}})_i}{\partial(\underline{\mathbf{def}})_j}; \quad (1.103)$$

and the matrix would be composed as:

$$\underline{\underline{\mathbf{K}}}_M = \begin{bmatrix} \frac{\partial \underline{\mathbf{S}}}{\partial \underline{\mathbf{F}}} & \frac{\partial \underline{\mathbf{S}}}{\partial \theta^3} & \underline{\mathbf{0}} \\ \frac{\partial s^3}{\partial \underline{\mathbf{F}}} & \frac{\partial s^3}{\partial \theta^3} & \underline{\mathbf{0}} \\ \underline{\mathbf{0}} & \underline{\mathbf{0}} & \frac{\partial \underline{\mathbf{M}}}{\partial \underline{\mathbf{\Gamma}}} \end{bmatrix} \quad (1.104)$$

where, due to the assumption done before, $\underline{\mathbf{M}}$ is a two-components vector containing the work conjugates to the $\partial \theta^3 / \partial x$ and $\partial \theta^3 / \partial y$ (M_{31} and M_{32} respectively). With the simplifications done so far, the element stiffness matrix would look like:

$$\underline{\underline{\mathbf{K}}} = \left[\begin{array}{c|c} \int_{\Omega_i} \left(\underline{\mathbf{B}}^{vT} \cdot \frac{\partial \underline{\mathbf{S}}}{\partial \underline{\mathbf{F}}} \cdot \underline{\mathbf{B}}^u \right) d\Omega & \int_{\Omega_i} \left(\underline{\mathbf{B}}^{vT} \cdot \frac{\partial \underline{\mathbf{S}}}{\partial \theta^3} \otimes \underline{\mathbf{N}}^\times \right) d\Omega \\ \hline - \int_{\Omega_i} \left(\underline{\mathbf{N}}^{\times T} \otimes \frac{\partial s^3}{\partial \underline{\mathbf{F}}} \cdot \underline{\mathbf{B}}^u \right) d\Omega & \int_{\Omega_i} \left(\underline{\mathbf{B}}^{\times T} \cdot \frac{\partial \underline{\mathbf{M}}}{\partial \underline{\mathbf{\Gamma}}} \cdot \underline{\mathbf{B}}^\times - \frac{\partial s^3}{\partial \theta^3} \underline{\mathbf{N}}^{\times T} \otimes \underline{\mathbf{N}}^\times \right) d\Omega \end{array} \right] \quad (1.105)$$

in which the terms that still require further derivation might be computed by using Equations 1.46, 1.47 and 1.48 as:

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{\partial S_{ij}}{\partial \theta^3} &= \frac{\partial}{\partial \theta^3} \left[\mathbf{R}_{ik} \# \sigma_{kl} \mathbf{R}_{ml} \left(\underline{\mathbf{F}}^{-T} \right)_{mj} \right] = \\ & \mathbf{R}'_{ik} \# \sigma_{kl} \mathbf{R}_{ml} \left(\underline{\mathbf{F}}^{-T} \right)_{mj} + \mathbf{R}_{ik} \frac{\partial \# \sigma_{kl}}{\partial \theta^3} \mathbf{R}_{ml} \left(\underline{\mathbf{F}}^{-T} \right)_{mj} + \mathbf{R}_{ik} \# \sigma_{kl} \mathbf{R}'_{ml} \left(\underline{\mathbf{F}}^{-T} \right)_{mj} = \\ & \# \sigma_{kl} \left[\mathbf{R}'_{ik} \mathbf{R}_{ml} \left(\underline{\mathbf{F}}^{-T} \right)_{mj} + \mathbf{R}_{ik} \mathbf{R}'_{ml} \left(\underline{\mathbf{F}}^{-T} \right)_{mj} \right] + \mathbf{R}_{ik} \frac{\partial \# \sigma_{kl}}{\partial \theta^3} \mathbf{R}_{ml} \left(\underline{\mathbf{F}}^{-T} \right)_{mj} = \\ & \# \sigma_{kl} \left[\mathbf{R}'_{ik} \left(\underline{\mathbf{R}}^T \underline{\mathbf{F}}^{-T} \right)_{lj} + \mathbf{R}_{ik} \left(\underline{\mathbf{R}}'^T \underline{\mathbf{F}}^{-T} \right)_{lj} \right] + \mathbf{R}_{ik} \frac{\partial \# \sigma_{kl}}{\partial \theta^3} \left(\underline{\mathbf{R}}^T \underline{\mathbf{F}}^{-T} \right)_{lj} = \\ & \left[\# \sigma_{kl} \mathbf{R}'_{ik} + \mathbf{R}_{ik} \frac{\partial \# \sigma_{kl}}{\partial \theta^3} \right] \left(\underline{\mathbf{R}}^T \underline{\mathbf{F}}^{-T} \right)_{lj} + \# \sigma_{kl} \mathbf{R}_{ik} \left(\underline{\mathbf{R}}'^T \underline{\mathbf{F}}^{-T} \right)_{lj}; \quad (1.106) \end{aligned}$$

that is equal to:

$$\frac{\partial \underline{\mathbf{S}}}{\partial \theta^3} = \left[\underline{\mathbf{R}}' \cdot \# \underline{\underline{\boldsymbol{\sigma}}} \cdot \underline{\mathbf{R}}^T + \underline{\mathbf{R}} \cdot \# \underline{\underline{\boldsymbol{\sigma}}} \cdot \underline{\mathbf{R}}'^T + \underline{\mathbf{R}} \cdot \frac{\partial \# \underline{\underline{\boldsymbol{\sigma}}}}{\partial \theta^3} \cdot \underline{\mathbf{R}}^T \right] \cdot \underline{\mathbf{F}}^{-T}; \quad (1.107)$$

$$\frac{\partial s^3}{\partial F_{kl}} = \frac{\partial}{\partial F_{kl}} \left[\left(\mathbf{R}^{\#} \underline{\sigma} \mathbf{R}^T \right)_{21} - \left(\mathbf{R}^{\#} \underline{\sigma} \mathbf{R}^T \right)_{12} \right] = \frac{\partial}{\partial F_{kl}} \left[R_{2i} \# \sigma_{ij} R_{1j} - R_{1i} \# \sigma_{ij} R_{2j} \right] = \frac{\partial \# \sigma_{ij}}{\partial F_{kl}} (R_{2i} R_{1j} - R_{1i} R_{2j}); \quad (1.108)$$

$$\frac{\partial s^3}{\partial \theta^3} = \frac{\partial}{\partial \theta^3} \left[\left(\mathbf{R}^{\#} \underline{\sigma} \mathbf{R}^T \right)_{21} - \left(\mathbf{R}^{\#} \underline{\sigma} \mathbf{R}^T \right)_{12} \right] = \frac{\partial}{\partial \theta^3} \left[R_{2i} \# \sigma_{ij} R_{1j} - R_{1i} \# \sigma_{ij} R_{2j} \right] = \# \sigma_{ij} \left[R'_{2i} R_{1j} - R'_{1i} R_{2j} + R_{2i} R'_{1j} - R_{1i} R'_{2j} \right] + \frac{\partial \# \sigma_{ij}}{\partial \theta^3} \left[R_{2i} R_{1j} - R_{1i} R_{2j} \right]; \quad (1.109)$$

$$\frac{\partial M_{ij}}{\partial \Gamma_{kl}} = \delta_{ik} \delta_{jl} \beta; \quad (1.110)$$

where R' can be found in Equation 1.86, and $\frac{\partial \# \sigma_{ij}}{\partial \theta^3}$ and $\frac{\partial \# \sigma_{ij}}{\partial F_{kl}}$ are the following:

$$\frac{\partial \# \sigma_{ij}}{\partial F_{kl}} = \frac{\partial}{\partial F_{kl}} \left[J \lambda (J - 1) \delta_{ij} + (\mu + \mu_c) (R_{mi} F_{mn} F_{pn} R_{pj}) + (\mu - \mu_c) (F_{mi} R_{mn} F_{pn} R_{pj}) - 2\mu F_{mi} R_{mj} \right] =$$

$$\delta_{ij} J \lambda \left[\left(\mathbf{F}_{kl}^{-T} \right)_{kl} (J - 1) + J \left(\mathbf{F}_{kl}^{-T} \right) \right] + (\mu + \mu_c) \left[R_{mi} \delta_{mk} \delta_{nl} F_{pn} R_{pj} + R_{mi} F_{mn} \delta_{pk} \delta_{nl} R_{pj} \right] + (\mu - \mu_c) \left[\delta_{mk} \delta_{il} R_{mn} F_{pn} R_{pj} + F_{mi} R_{mn} \delta_{pk} \delta_{nl} R_{pj} \right] - 2\mu \delta_{mk} \delta_{il} R_{mj} =$$

$$\left(\lambda \delta_{ij} \left(\mathbf{F}^{-T} \right)_{kl} J \right) [2J - 1] + (\mu + \mu_c) \left[R_{ki} \left(\mathbf{F}^T \mathbf{R} \right)_{lj} + \left(\mathbf{R}^T \mathbf{F} \right)_{il} R_{kj} \right] + (\mu - \mu_c) \left[\delta_{il} \left(\mathbf{R} \mathbf{F}^T \mathbf{R} \right)_{kj} + \left(\mathbf{F}^T \mathbf{R} \right)_{il} R_{kj} \right] - 2\mu \delta_{il} R_{kj}; \quad (1.111)$$

$$\frac{\partial \# \underline{\sigma}}{\partial \theta^3} = (\mu + \mu_c) \left[\mathbf{R}'^T \cdot \mathbf{F} \cdot \mathbf{F}^T \cdot \mathbf{R} + \mathbf{R}^T \cdot \mathbf{F} \cdot \mathbf{F}^T \cdot \mathbf{R}' \right] + (\mu - \mu_c) \left[\mathbf{F}^T \cdot \mathbf{R}' \cdot \mathbf{F}^T \cdot \mathbf{R} + \mathbf{F}^T \cdot \mathbf{R} \cdot \mathbf{F}^T \cdot \mathbf{R}' \right] - 2\mu \mathbf{F}^T \cdot \mathbf{R}'; \quad (1.112)$$

Chapter 2

Tests

This chapter includes the tests performed to verify the correctness of the implemented formulation. In the following two sections homogeneous-field and not-homogeneous field bench tests will be presented. The main objective in the FEM implementation is to provide the software with the element stiffness matrix and the external force vector, that are Equations 1.76, 1.77 and 1.78. The formulation has been implemented in the software Z-SET, in which it was possible to include the Finite Element as an Object in a C++ environment by mean of dynamic libraries. The outcomes of the tests have been compared with the results relative to the Small Displacement formulation that was already implemented in the software.

2.1 Homogeneous Fields - Single Element Tests

2.1.1 Tension Test

The tensile tests is meant to verify the correctness of the part of the stiffness matrix that acts on the displacement degrees of freedom. A single square element of 1 mm long edge has been used. The element has 8 nodes, thus 24 DOFs, of which 16 are relative to in-plane displacements u_1 and u_2 and the other 8 are relative to the only allowed rotation in a 2D space, that is θ_3 . The left bottom corner of the Element has coordinates $\{0;0\}$ and the top right corner lies in $\{1;1\}$. Homogeneous deformation fields been achieved through application of the following BCs:

$$\begin{cases} u_1 = 0 \text{ mm} & @x = 0; \\ u_1 = 4 \text{ mm} & @x = 1; \\ u_2 = 0 \text{ mm} & @y = 0; \\ \theta_3 = 0 \text{ rad} & @x = 0; \end{cases} \quad (2.1)$$

ideally leading to an equivalent tensile strain (if measured under small deformation assumption) of 4. The mechanical properties used to run this bench test are summarized in Table 2.1. As expected, when large deformations are applied, the SD framework is not anymore reliable. As reported in Figure 2.1a the Element linearly shrinks along the y direction and reaches a point in which the thickness becomes null. The simulation continues and the top nodes are brought below the bottom ones. This condition occurs due to the fact that in a SD simulation the deformations are expected to be be small so that a check of

λ [MPa]	μ	μ_c [MPa]	β [kg/m ³]
114000.0	0.3	114000.0	4428.0

Table 2.1: Elastic material properties used to run the bench test.

(a) Deformation history of the single element tensile test in a SD framework.

(b) Deformation history of the single element tensile test in a SD framework.

Figure 2.2: Load-displacement graph of the tensile test on a single element. Comparison of SD and LD formulation.

Formulation	σ_{11} [MPa]	σ_{22} [MPa]	σ_{12} [MPa]	σ_{21} [MPa]	σ_{33} [MPa]
SD	307692	0	0	0	92308
LD	909594	0	0	0	7845

Table 2.2: Predicted components of the stress tensor in SD and LD framework at the end of the tensile test.

Formulation	σ_{11} [MPa]	σ_{22} [MPa]	σ_{12} [MPa]	σ_{21} [MPa]	σ_{33} [MPa]
SD	0	0	53846	53846	0
LD	155250	15528	69861	68886	0

Table 2.3: Predicted components of the stress tensor in SD and LD framework at the end of the glide test.

the Jacobian is not required. On the contrary, the non-linear shrinkage of the element along the y-axis has been perfectly captured by the LD formulation as it has been reported in Figure 2.1b. The results in terms of load-displacement are reported in Figure 2.1c, where it is appreciable that, as expected, the two curves diverge from each due to the nonlinearity. In Table 2.2 the differences in terms of predicted behavior of the Element between SD and LD at the end of the test are reported.

2.1.2 Glide Test

This test is meant to verify the correctness of the implementation of the terms related to the rotational degrees of freedom. The geometry and the mechanical properties used for this test are the same as the ones used of for the tensile test. A homogeneous shear field is induced in the element by applying the following boundary conditions:

$$\begin{cases} u_1 = 0 \text{ mm} & @y = 0; \\ u_1 = 2 \text{ mm} & @y = 1; \\ u_2 = 0 \text{ mm} & @y = 0; \\ u_2 = 04 \text{ mm} & @y = 1; \end{cases} \quad (2.2)$$

Ideally, this set of BCs shall induce the Element to return an equivalent shear strain of 1 in a SD framework. This value was indeed reproduced during the SD test. The micro-rotation was left free to follow the macro-rotation, therefore the micro-rotation was expected to have opposite value of the macro-rotation in the whole element. This condition was verified in the SD test, where the micro-rotation had an homogeneous value of -1. As expected, the LD test produced a smaller but uniform micro rotation value equal to 0.7878. In Figure 2.2b it is observable the deformed configuration of the Element during the glide test. The tests performed under SD and LD conditions produced the same deformed configuration, but the difference between the two formulations can be found in the different predicted value of micro-rotation. In Figure 2.2a the load-displacement curves are reported for the glide test performed under LD and SD. It is evident that the LD is able to capture the additional tensile stiffness induced by the geometrical nonlinearity of the test.

2.2 Simple Micro-rotation Boundary Layer

This test aims at verifying the element formulation in a multi-element test, in which also the gradient of the rotation is involved. The geometry of the performed test is pictured in Figure 2.4. The following

Figure 2.3: Undeformed and Deformed shape assumed by the Element during the glide test (a). Load-displacement graph of the glide test on a single element. Comparison of SD and LD formulation (b).

Figure 2.4: Comparison of the predicted distribution of the θ_3 field along the y-direction of the specimen using LD and SD formulations.

BCs have been applied:

$$\begin{cases} u_1 = 0 \text{ mm} & @y = 0; \\ u_2 = 0 \text{ mm} & @y = 0; \\ \theta_3 = 0 \text{ rad} & @y = 0; \\ u_2 = 0 \text{ mm} & @y = 1; \\ \theta_3 = 0.01 \text{ rad} & @y = 1; \end{cases} \quad (2.3)$$

The generated deformation fields are not homogeneous anymore, this means that in this test we can observe the effect of the gradient of the micro-rotation and also verify its implementation. As the previous tests, this as well has been tested against the results coming from the SD simulation. The distribution of the micro-rotation through along the y-direction has been chosen as the feature to verify the correctness of the formulation. In Figure 2.3 this comparison is reported, and it can be appreciated that the produced fields are identical. Obviously, the predicted distribution of SD and LD formulations are the same because the applied rotation is still very small (≈ 0.5 deg). Larger angles would induce appreciable difference in the predicted rotation fields. In Figures 2.5 and 2.6 are reported the predicted wryness fields using a SD and a LD framework. The reproduced fields can be assumed as identical because, once again, the applied micro-rotation is quite small. This nonetheless proves the correctness of the developed LD model since

Figure 2.5: Geometry used for the micro-rotation boundary layer test. Units are in millimeters.

Figure 2.6: Predicted field of Γ_{32} using a Cosserat SD theory. Units are mm^{-1} .

it is retrieving the SD results for small applied deformations.

Figure 2.7: Predicted field of Γ_{32} using a Cosserat LD theory. Units are mm^{-1} .

Appendix A

A.1 Recalls of Tensorial Algebra and Tensorial Differentiation

The Levi-Civita Symbol, or permutation symbol, is given as:

$$\epsilon_{ijk} = \begin{cases} 1 & \text{for } (i,j,k) = (1,2,3) \text{ or } (2,3,1) \text{ or } (3,2,1) \\ -1 & \text{for } (i,j,k) = (3,2,1) \text{ or } (2,1,3) \text{ or } (1,3,2) \\ 0 & \text{otherwise} \end{cases} \quad (\text{A.1})$$

and it enjoys the following properties:

$$\epsilon_{ijk} = -\epsilon_{ikj} = \epsilon_{kij}; \quad (\text{A.2})$$

$$\epsilon_{ijk}\epsilon_{imn} = \delta_{jm}\delta_{kn} - \delta_{jn}\delta_{km}; \quad (\text{A.3})$$

and it is also used to define the cross product between two first order tensors as:

$$\underline{\mathbf{a}} \times \underline{\mathbf{b}} = \underline{\mathbf{c}} \iff c_i = \epsilon_{ijk}a_jb_k; \quad (\text{A.4})$$

Skew-symmetric second order tensors, due to the fact that they contain only three non-zero entries, can be handled through a vector that incorporates the same informations and vice-versa. Given a general skew-symmetric tensor $\underline{\mathbf{W}}$, the following is valid:

$$\underline{\mathbf{w}} = -\frac{1}{2}\underline{\underline{\epsilon}} : \underline{\mathbf{W}}; \quad (\text{A.5})$$

$$\underline{\mathbf{W}} = -\underline{\underline{\epsilon}} \cdot \underline{\mathbf{w}}; \quad (\text{A.6})$$

where the vector $\underline{\mathbf{w}}$ contains the three non-zero entries of the tensor $\underline{\mathbf{W}}$.

In the report, it was necessary to determine the variation of the determinant of a second order tensor with respect to the entries of the tensor, and this was evaluated using the following Jacobi's formula:

$$\det(\underline{\underline{\mathbf{A}}}) = \text{tr}(\text{Adj}(\underline{\underline{\mathbf{A}}}) \cdot d\underline{\underline{\mathbf{A}}}); \quad (\text{A.7})$$

which, since $\text{Adj}(\underline{\underline{\mathbf{A}}}) = \det(\underline{\underline{\mathbf{A}}})\underline{\underline{\mathbf{A}}}^{-1}$, particularizes into:

$$\frac{\partial \det \underline{\underline{\mathbf{A}}}}{\partial \underline{\underline{\mathbf{A}}}} = \det \underline{\underline{\mathbf{A}}}\underline{\underline{\mathbf{A}}}^{-T}; \quad (\text{A.8})$$

Another Equation that has been used in the report expresses the variation of the inverse of a second order tensor with respect to the entries of the tensor, and it can be obtained by differentiating the following:

$$\underline{\underline{\mathbf{F}}} \cdot \underline{\underline{\mathbf{F}}}^{-1} = \underline{\underline{\mathbf{I}}}; \quad (\text{A.9})$$

with respect to a general real number, α , thus obtaining:

$$\frac{\partial \tilde{\mathbf{F}}}{\partial \alpha} \cdot \tilde{\mathbf{F}}^{-1} + \tilde{\mathbf{F}} \cdot \frac{\partial \tilde{\mathbf{F}}^{-1}}{\partial \alpha} = \mathbf{0}; \Rightarrow \frac{\partial \tilde{\mathbf{F}}^{-1}}{\partial \alpha} = -\tilde{\mathbf{F}}^{-1} \cdot \frac{\partial \tilde{\mathbf{F}}}{\partial \alpha} \cdot \tilde{\mathbf{F}}^{-1}; \quad (\text{A.10})$$

that can be generalized to $\tilde{\mathbf{F}}$ and obtain:

$$\frac{\partial \left(\tilde{\mathbf{F}}^{-1} \right)_{ij}}{\partial F_{kl}} = -\tilde{\mathbf{F}}^{-1}_{ik} \tilde{\mathbf{F}}^{-1}_{lj}; \quad (\text{A.11})$$

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